

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TYPHA DOMINGENSIS (SOUTHERN CATTAIL) REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Typha domingens fibre was extracted from the leaves by water retting method for 15 days, portion of the fibre was subjected to alkali, acetylation, permanganate and silane treatments. Epoxy resin (BADGE) was used as matrix to fabricate the composite via hand lay-up method using the treated and untreated fibre. Tensile and flexural tests were conducted and evaluated on the composites and the result obtained shows increase in tensile and flexural strengths, the untreated short typha fibre composite had the least tensile strength of 18MPa and highest value of 29MPa was obtained in the silane treated fibre composites. Flexural strength also shows 287MPa and 411MPa in the untreated compared to silane treated composites respectively. FTIR analysis was used to characterize the composites and the spectra shows changes in peaks, indicating modification of the fibre as well as fibre-matrix interaction. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to evaluate the morphology of the composites and the result obtained shows different morphology in the treated and untreated typha fibre composites indicating successful chemical treatment as well as fibre-matrix interaction. Hence, chemical modification of typha fibre has been found to improve mechanical properties of the composite and the fibre has very good potentials for use as reinforcement in composites. The composites have potential application in construction, furniture and automobiles.

KEYWORDS

Typha, Epoxy, Hand lay-up, FTIR and Composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, interest has been strongly displayed in the use of lignocellulose fibre as reinforcement in various polymeric matrices. The subject of interest for several years has been biodegradable polymers due to their potential to protect the environment because incineration of components having natural fibre uses 45% less energy, resulting in lower emission as shown in a study. The fibres are also found to be renewable and are in expensive, hence natural fibre composites have replaced so many conventional materials in several areas like construction, transportation, consumer goods among others. This is due to their light weight, flexibility and ease of fabrication into various shapes with less cost (Salihin, *et al.*, 2013). Metals, ceramics and polymers have been found to be the basic groups of materials used in composite fabrication, a combination of any two or more of materials in these groups produces very effective composite (Ratna, 2015). Although, agricultural waste materials tend to pose problems in the environment, most of which are lignocellulose in nature, these include rice husk, corn stalk among others. Utilization of agricultural biomaterials in composites will help in sanitizing the environment, lead to growth and stability of a country's economy (Azimah *et al*, 2013). Hence, Natural fibre reinforced composite" refers to natural fibre embedded in any polymeric matrix (thermoplastic or

thermoset, natural or synthetic). These composites are found to be eco-friendly to a greater degree. However, several factors determine the formulation of effective biocomposites, these includes good fabrication technique, effective fibre and or matrix modification by blending and functionalization, a process known as “Tricorner synergism” (Naheed, *et al.*, 2014). Earlier reported matrices include high density polyethylene (HDPE), low density polyethylene (LDPE), polypropylene (PP), polyetherketone (PEEK) among others. In composites, earlier used reinforcements includes glass, carbon, aluminum oxides and other plant fibres such as like flax, hemp and jute, amongst others. Properties of the fibre such as aspect ratio, thermal stability and fibre-matrix interface are key factors that govern the properties of the composites. More so, surface adhesion between the fibre as reinforcement and the polymer matrix plays vital roles in stress transmission from the matrix to the fibre, this contributes towards the effective performance of the composite (Salisu *et al.*, 2016). Salihin *et al.*, (2015) studied the effect of tert-butyl perbenzoate (TBP) on the tensile and flexural properties of sugarcane baggase reinforced polyester composites, TBP was used as catalyst at elevated temperature of 110 °C, the sugarcane baggase fibre were treated with 1, 3 and 5% NaOH and combined with fibre loading formulation of 0, 20, 30 and 40 php and hot pressed to form the composite. 3% NaOH baggase composite gave higher tensile strength and tensile modulus while the untreated gave the least. Yusrina, *et al.*, (2013) studied the mechanical and thermal ageing resistance of microcrystalline cellulose-palm reinforced polyester composite, using methyl ethyl Ketone Peroxide as catalyst. A layer of the composite (i.e microcrystalline cellulose as filler) was used to improve the mechanical properties of the composite. Typha domingensis is found mostly on wet lands, sewage water in open places and also on lands where waste materials are dumped. It is a perennial plant, grows between 1 to 3 meters in length, possess spongy strap-like leaves and is abundant in nature and also renewable. Typha has the ability to absorb harmful water such as industrial and domestic effluent. It is cultivated on all types of soils having different pH ranges, but not under shade (Ponnukrishnan *et al.*, 2014).

This paper is an extract from my Ph.d research, as a student with the department of Pure and Industrial chemistry, Bayero University, Kano. In this research, the typha fibre was chemically treated with Sodium hydroxide, Acetic acid, Potassium permanganate and Silane. The mechanical properties of the fabricated composites where tested to ascertain the effect of fibre modification in the composites and the subsequent effect of modification on fibre-matrix interaction as reported in other research work (Salihin *et al.*, (2015); (Naidu and Rao, 2016).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Typha leaves were collected from Hauren shanu of Gwale local government and extracted by water retting method. Typha leaves were submerged in a trough of water for 15 days as shown in Figs. 2.1(a). Water penetrating the central stalk portion results in swelling of the inner cells and subsequent bursting the outermost layer, this increases absorption of moisture and decay-producing bacteria. Scutching with a sharp object followed by carding with soft nylon brush was done to extract the fibre. Washing severally with clean tap water and drying under shade for 3days, followed by brushing gives fine strands of the fibre as shown in Figs. 2.1(b). The fibre obtained was further processed to give the desired size for the composite fabrication as shown in Figs. 2.1(c-d) (Luigi, 2013 and Salisu *et al.*, 2015).

Fig. 2.1: (a). Typha plant (b) Retting of Typha (c) Extracted Typha fibres
(d) Processed Short Typha fibres

2.2. Fibre treatment

Some portions of the fibre was first treated with alkali and further treated with acetic acid, Permanganate and Silane reagents.

- **Alkali Treatment**

The extracted fibre was immersed in 5% NaOH solution for 1 hour, the activated O-H groups on the cellulosic fibre were replaced by Na⁺ of the alkali leading to fibre modification as shown in scheme 1. The fibre was then rinsed with distilled water and washed with very dilute acid (HCl) to remove any excess alkali, followed by rinsing finally with distilled water until the fibre are alkali free. The washed fibre was dried under shadow. Some portion of the dried alkali treated fibre was further silylated (Yakasai, 2014), acetylated and treated with permanganate. The reaction is illustrated in scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Reaction between cellulosic fibre and alkali (Yakasai, 2014).

- **Acetylation**

Alkali-pretreated fibre was soaked in glacial acetic (10%) acid for 1 hr at 30 °C, it was decanted and soaked in acetic anhydride (14%) containing one drop of concentrated H₂SO₄ for 5 minutes as reported by Susheel *et al.*, (2009). Scheme 2 shows the reaction that occurred.

Scheme 2: Reaction of acetic anhydride with hydroxyl groups of fibre (Naidu and Rao (2016); Susheel, 2009).

- **Permanganate treatment**

Alkali pre-treated typha fibre were soaked in permanganate solution at concentration 0.05 % in acetone for 1 min, the KMnO₄ drained and the fibre dried under shade (Mohanta and Archaya, 2016).

- **Silane Treatment**

1% phenyltriethoxysilane solution in acetone was prepared. Acetone promotes hydrolysis better than water and this allows silylation to take place in presence of moisture on the surface of the fibre rather than with the carrier. Acetic acid was added to the solution to maintain a pH of 4 and stirred for 10mins. Portion of the dried alkali pre-treated fibre was immersed in the solution for 1hour, the fibre was removed from the solution and dried in hot air oven at 60°C (Salisu *et al.*, 2016).

2.3. Matrix formation and Composite Fabrication

Epoxy resin (BADGE) of the grade LM-556 with a density of 1.5 g/cm³ mix with hardener HY-951(TETA) in a ratio of 2:1 was used as the matrix material, petroleum jelly as a debonding agent. Short typha fibre of 0.5-1.5mm length was poured into the epoxy resin (Azimah, 2013), manually stirred, followed by addition of the hardener and stirring continues. The paste was poured into the mold and spread homogeneously and allowed to cure at room temperature before removal of the composite (Salisu *et al.*, 2015 and Yakasai, 2014). In each mixture, ratio of resin 100phr (per hundred resin), fibre of 5phr was used (Yusrina *et al.*, 2013 and Noor, *et al.*, 2013).

2.4. Tests and Analysis

2.4.1. Tensile Strength

Tensile strength of the short Typha fibre was conducted according to ASTM-D 3039M using Ultimate testing machine (UTM) Shimadzu (MODEL AG-1) at the department of mechanical engineering, Bayero university Kano. Tensile test was carried out to determine the tensile strength, percentage elongation and tensile modulus values using 100 kN capacity load cell and parallel vice grips. The specimen size was (250×25×3) mm, a span of 150 mm, a cross-head speed of 2mm/min. The test was performed until tensile failure. Tensile property was determined for six different specimens of each sample composite and an average of five replicate of the tested specimens was presented. Force and displacement values were recorded simultaneously

during the test and the tensile parameters were calculated using standard (Daramola *et al.*, 2017).

The tensile strength was evaluated using the expressions in equ. (3)

$$\text{Tensile Strength (MPa)} = \frac{\text{Load at break}}{\text{Cross-sectional Area}} \dots\dots(3) \text{ (Daramola, et al., 2017)}$$

Fig. 2.4.1. Tensile strength Samples (a) Before Test (b) After Test (c) Ultimate Testing Machine (UTM).

2.4.2. Flexural Test

Flexural strength was conducted according to ASTM-D 790-97A standards using the same equipment as in the tensile test. A three point test method in accordance with the standard procedure was employed at a cross head speed of 2mm/min and a support of 50mm. The samples were cut into rectangular specimens of size (125 × 12.7 × 3.2) mm using diamond cutter and then milled. Presence of extensometer gives the machine the ability to elongate the sample at constant rate and simultaneously measure the load applied as well as the resulting elongations. The test determines the bending property of the composite (Shakuntala, 2014).

The flexural strength was evaluated as shown in equ. 4

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{(3P_{\max}L)}{bt^2} \dots\dots\dots (4) \text{ (Shakuntala, 2014; Aditya and Prasad, 2017).}$$

Where:

P_{\max} = Force at break

L = Support span

b = Breadth of sample

t = Thickness of sample

Fig. 2.4.2. Flexural test samples (a) Before test (b) After test

2.4.3. FTIR

The Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometry (FTIR) was used to evaluate the interface and morphology of the fibre before and after treatment with various reagents, in other to ascertain the reactions that have taken place on the fibre. The horizontal attenuated totally reflectance fourier transform spectroscopy technique (FTIR-HATR) was employed with a Cary 630 FTIR machine of Agilant Technology, at the Department of Chemistry Bayero University Kano, in accordance with Yakasai (2014) and Reddy (2017).

2.5. Results

Fig. 2.5.3a. SEM photomicrograph of fractured Untreated Short Typha fibre composite. (ai) 200X (aii) 500X

Fig. 2.5.3b: SEM photomicrograph of fractured Alkali treated Short Typha fibre composite. (bi) 200X (bii) 500X

3. DISCUSSION

3.1. Tensile Strength

The use of suitable reagents modifies the fibre as well as the mechanical properties of the composites. The fibre becomes more hydrophobic, its tensile strength increases thereby improving the interfacial adhesion between the typha and moringa fibre with the matrix (Yakasai, 2014).

Fig.2.5.1a shows the tensile strength of treated and untreated fibre composite. The untreated short typha fibre showed the least tensile property of 18MP. This is due to weak compatibility between the fibre and the matrix brought about by the presence of hemicellulose, lignin and pectin. Highest values of 29MPa was recorded in the silane treated fibre composites. This is due to reaction taking place between silane and moisture in presence of the fibre, resulting in the formation of silanol, which has the ability to condense with adjacent silanol group (Si-O-Si), thereby forming a cross-linked network of covalent bonds between the matrix and the silylated fibre. The number of hydroxyl groups of the cellulose on the fibre is also reduced, as such adherence of the fibre to the matrix and interfacial strength increases. Other treated fibre composites also displayed good tensile strength. Treatment of fibre with alkali increases fibre-

matrix interaction because there is partial removal of lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose. The structure of the fibre filaments is tempered with, as such increase in surface area available for contact with the matrix occurs (Yakasai, 2014). Pre-treatment with acetic anhydride results in substitution of the polymer hydroxyl groups (OH) of the fibre with acetyl groups (CH₃CO), this makes the fibre more hydrophobic and also improves mechanical properties of the composites (Susheel, 2009; Naidu and Rao, 2016). Permanganate treatment of fibre reduces the water absorption property of the fibre. It has been found to be among the best methods to improve fibre-matrix interaction (Susheel, 2009; Mohanta and Archaya, 2016). The findings in this research is consistent with the work of Njoku and Obikwelu, (2008), Pai and Jagtap, (2015), Salisu *et al.*, (2015), Mohanta and Acharya, (2016) on fibre surface treatment: its effect on structural, thermal, and mechanical properties of luffa cylindrica fibre and its composite, Yakasai, *et al.*, (2016) and Daramola, *et al.*, (2017).

3.2. Flexural Strength

In Fig. 2.5.1b, the least strength was observed in the untreated short typha fibre having 287MPa while silane treated fibre had the highest values of 411MPa. A similar trend was observed as that in the tensile strength with reasons being the same. The results obtained are in accordance with the findings of Uma, (2012) where surface modification improved the mechanical properties of Tamarind fibre epoxy composite, Omole and Dauda, (2016) on physical and mechanical properties of chemically treated bagasse fibre as filler in unsaturated polyester composite, Salisu, *et al.*, (2016), Sathish *et al.*, (2017), Daramola, *et al.*, (2018), Hany *et al.*, (2018) and Silva *et al.*, (2018) on processing and properties of natural fibres reinforced thermoplastic and thermosetting composites. Hence, chemical modification improved the flexural strength of the composites.

3.3. FTIR

The surface chemical structure and interaction between the reinforcement and matrix in the composites were investigated using FT-IR as illustrated by the representative spectra in Fig. 2.5.2. The peaks at about 3365, 2868, 1611, 1235, and 832 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the –OH, C–H, C=O, C–O and C–OH, respectively in the untreated Typha fibre in Fig. 2.5.2a. In Fig.2.5.2b, a shift to 3361 for the –OH was observed due to partial removal of lignin resulting in reduction in the number of OH groups, the C–H stretching vibration absorption peak shifted from 2868 to 2858 cm⁻¹, a peak at 1462 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the CH₂ deformation in cellulose, 1611 cm⁻¹ was ascribed to C=O aldehyde group of lignin, 1235 cm⁻¹ was ascribed to the C–O stretching vibration of acetyl groups in lignin. The variation among the FTIR spectra could be associated with the change in the surface of the fibre brought about by alkali treatment. A broadening at 3391 cm⁻¹ is attributed to increase in number of –OH due to reaction with acetic acid, 1741 cm⁻¹ attributed to C=O acetyl group formed on the fibre and a reduction from 832 to 829 cm⁻¹ was observed, while treatment of the fibre with silane resulted in Si-O formation with peaks at 3400 cm⁻¹ and 829 cm⁻¹. This result is in accordance with the studies of Gejo, (2012), Yakasai, (2014), Naheed *et al.*, (2015), Sahari and Maleque, (2016) and Kai, (2018) on thermal and Mechanical Properties of Bamboo Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites.

3.4. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

In the SEM images presented in Fig. 2.5.3a, morphology of the composites indicates poor fibre-matrix interaction between the untreated short typha fibre and the matrix, fibre pull-out was observed, this may be attributed to presence of impurities and irregularities such as waxes and lignin having node-like structure resulting to poor adhesion between the fibre and the matrix. Pull-out holes in composites results in bonding failure and subsequent cracking. Micro-cracks resulting from plateaus, tongues and valley's at various elevations, having convex contours and

possessing edges indicating grain boundaries of nucleating cracks were also observed (Iheaturu, 2017). The alkali treated fibre composite in Fig. 2.5.3b shows a better bonding exist between the fibre and the matrix, a rough surface was also observed. This is due to partial removal of impurities and irregularities from the fibre surface, this improved the fibre matrix interaction (Rajasekaran *et al.*, 2017). Micro-pores were observed, resulting from fibre treatment which led to partial removal of lignin and hemicellulose. Similarly, an excellent fibre-matrix interaction brought about by covalent bond between the silane treated fibre and the matrix (Salisu *et al.*, 2016) was observed. The photomicrograph of the silane treated fibre composite shows absence of pores as well as cracks indicating good fibre shear or tear. All the morphologies were supported by the FTIR and mechanical tests conducted on the composites because good adhesion shows fibre tearing and fracture, due to high tensile strength. It can be inferred that surface modification affects the mechanical properties and the morphology of the composites. The result in this study is consistent with the findings of Kai *et al.*, (2018), Hany *et al.*, (2018), Iheaturu, (2017), Rajasekaran *et al.*, (2017), Salisu *et al.*, (2016), Pai and Jagtap (2015).

CONCLUSIONS

Extraction of typha fibre by water retting method as well as chemical modification of the fibres were successful, mechanical properties of the composites fabricated using the short typha fibres by hand lay-up technique were observed to increase in the treated fibre composites compared to untreated. FTIR result shows presence of various groups attached to the typha fibre compared to the untreated, indicating successful fibre modification which lead to better reinforcement-matrix interaction. Morphology of the composites was evaluated using SEM, it was observed that the treated and untreated fibres composites showed different morphology, indicating fibre modification. In conclusion, high strength typha composites have been successfully fabricated and analysed and based on the results obtained, the composites can have potential applications in furniture, construction and automobile.

RECOMMENDATION

The composites can be subjected to physical and mechanical analysis such as harness, impact, moisture absorption and chemical resistance to fully evaluate the composite for use in various area.

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